

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
BOUNCING BALL CONTENT PROJECT
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)**

Date: 2022/01/17

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 COMPUTER GRAPHICS

- Graphics provides one of the most natural means of communicating with a computer, since our highly developed 2D Or 3D pattern-recognition abilities allow us to perceive and process pictorial data rapidly.
- Computers have become a powerful medium for the rapid and economical production of pictures.
- Graphics provide a so natural means of communicating with the computer that they have become widespread.
- Interactive graphics is the most important means of producing pictures since the invention of photography and television .
- We can make pictures of not only the real world objects but also of abstract objects such as mathematical surfaces on 4D and of data that have no inherent geometry.
- A computer graphics system is a computer system with all the components of the general purpose computer system. There are five major elements in system: input devices, processor, memory, frame buffer, output devices.

Figure 1.1 Components of Computer Graphics

1.2 OPENGL TECHNOLOGY

OpenGL is the premier environment for developing portable, interactive 2D and 3D graphics applications. Since its introduction in 1992, OpenGL has become the industry's most widely used and supported 2D and 3D graphics application programming interface (API), bringing thousands of applications to a wide variety of computer platforms.

OpenGL fosters innovation and speeds application development by incorporating a broad set of rendering, texture mapping, special effects, and other powerful visualization functions. Developers can leverage the power of OpenGL across all popular desktop and workstation platforms, ensuring wide application deployment.

OpenGL Available Everywhere: Supported on all UNIX® workstations, and shipped standard with every Windows 95/98/2000/NT and MacOS PC, no other graphics API operates on a wider range of hardware platforms and software environments.

OpenGL runs on every major operating system including Mac OS, OS/2, UNIX, Windows 95/98, Windows 2000, Windows NT, Linux, Open Step, and BeOS; it also works with every major windowing system, including Win32, MacOS, Presentation Manager, and X-Window System. OpenGL is callable from Ada, C, C++, Fortran, Python, Perl and Java and offers complete independence from network protocols and topologies.

Figure 1.2 The openGL Interface

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

Computer graphics started with the display of data on hardcopy plotters and cathode ray tube (CRT) screens soon after the introduction of computers.

Computer graphics today largely interactive, the user controls the contents, structure, and appearance of objects and of displayed images by using input devices, such as keyboard, mouse, or touch-sensitive panel on the screen. Graphics based user interfaces allow millions of new users to control simple, low-cost application programs, such as spreadsheets, word processors, and drawing programs.

OpenGL (Open Graphics Library) is a standard specification defining a cross language, cross-platform API for writing applications that produce 2D and 3D computer graphics. The interface consists of over 250 different function calls which can be used to draw complex three-dimensional scenes from simple primitives. OpenGL was developed by Silicon Graphics Inc. (SGI) in 1992 and is widely used in CAD, virtual reality, scientific visualization, information visualization, and flight simulation. It is also used in video games, where it competes with Direct3D on Microsoft Windows platforms (see Direct3D vs. OpenGL). OpenGL is managed by the non-profit technology consortium, the Khronos Group.

In the 1980s, developing software that could function with a wide range of graphics hardware was a real challenge. By the early 1990s, Silicon Graphics (SGI) was a leader in 3D graphics for workstations. SGI's competitors (including Sun Microsystems, Hewlett-Packard and IBM) were also able. In addition, SGI had a large number of software customers; by changing to the OpenGL API they planned to keep their customers locked onto SGI (and IBM) hardware for a few years while market support for OpenGL matured to bring to market 3D hardware, supported by extensions made to the PHIGS standard. In 1992, SGI led the creation of the OpenGL architectural review board (OpenGL ARB), the group of companies that would maintain and expand the .

OpenGL specification took for years to come. On 17 December 1997, Microsoft and SGI initiated the Fahrenheit project, which was a joint effort with the goal of unifying the OpenGL and Direct3D interfaces (and adding a scene-graph API too). In 1998 HewlettPackard joined the project.[4] It initially showed some promise of bringing order to the world of interactive 3D.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS & SPECIFICATION

3.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

Minimum hardware specification

- Microprocessor: 1.0 GHz and above CPU based on either AMD or INTEL Microprocessor Architecture
- Main memory : 512 MB RAM
- Hard Disk : 40 GB
- Hard disk speed in RPM:5400 RPM
- Keyboard: QWERTY Keyboard
- Mouse :2 or 3 Button mouse
- Monitor : 1024 x 768 display resolution

3.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

Minimum software specification

- Operating system : Windows (Any)
- Tool Used : Dev C++
- OPENGL Library
- Mouse Driver
- Graphics Driver
- C++ Language

CHAPTER 4

DESIGN

4.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

Existing system for a graphics is the TC++. This system will support only the 2D graphics. 2D graphics package being designed should be easy to use and understand. It should provide various options such as free hand drawing, line drawing, polygon drawing, filled polygons, flood fill, translation, rotation, scaling, clipping etc. Even though these properties were supported, it was difficult to render 2D graphics cannot be very difficult to get a 3 Dimensional object. Even the effects like lighting, shading cannot be provided. So we go for Dev C++.

4.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

To achieve three dimensional effects, open GL software is proposed. It is software which provides a graphical interface. It is a interface between application program and graphics hardware. The advantages are:

1. Open GL is designed as a streamlined.
2. It's a hardware independent interface i.e it can be implemented on many different hardware platforms.
3. With OpenGL we can draw a small set of geometric primitives such as points, lines and polygons etc.
4. It provides double buffering which is vital in providing transformations.
5. It is event driven software.
6. It provides call back function.

4.3 WHAT WE ARE DEVELOPING?

First the floor is drawn which is a checkerboard, most likely similar to our opengl chess board program. Then we will draw three balls, of different colors. These balls will bounce up and down on the floor. To make the program or interesting, the user interaction has been added to it. With the help of four navigation key, the floor as well as ball, the whole system can be zoom in/out and can also be move around - simply say moves the camera in different directions - swinging the camera around.

Basically, we are creating an application which shows the balls bouncing on a floor. The animation which make application more interesting, with arrow keys move the camera.

4.4 PROJECT MODULES

Apart from the basic modules of a gl programming i.e header files, main function this application has basically in 5 modules. We have defined global array for Colors to be used for balls and floor.

```
// Colors
```

```
GLfloat WHITE[] = {1, 1, 1};
```

```
GLfloat RED[] = {1, 0, 0};
```

```
GLfloat GREEN[] = {0, 1, 0};
```

```
GLfloat MAGENTA[] = {1, 0, 1}
```

1. CAMERA CLASS - This class will define the methods (functions) that are to be used for movement of camera. The camera moves horizontally in a circle centered at the origin of radius 10. It moves vertically straight up and down.

Here some use of trigonometry comes as we apply the formula with sine and cosine functions from opengl. The variables are defined which will store the position of the camera, it's x-y-z positions. The swing or motion of camera done via the angle, which determine x,z position. Angle will help movement of camera in and around. While the value of y coordinate helps in moving camera up and down.

The functions prototype here will get the information and determine the position of x, y, z coordinate of camera. Also prototype will define animation, movement in four direction - up, down, left and right.

2. BALL CLASS - All the variable and prototype function declared for the balls. A ball has a radius, a color, and bounces up and down between a maximum height and the xz plane. Therefore the x and z coordinates of the balls are fixed. It uses a lame bouncing algorithm, simply moving up or down by a mere 0.05 units at each frame.

The prototype of function that will draw the ball will have following parameters - radius, color, x, y, z. Here x-y-z are coordinate positions. The ball is given a good shape with call of glutSolidSphere .

3. CHECKERBOARD CLASS - We all know a checkerboard is one with alternate square of two different color. This class will define methods and variable for checkerboard. The number of squares in the checkerboard is set via constructor. Each of the square in checkerboard is 1 x 1 unit. The one of it's corner is (0, 0) and the board stretches out along positive x and positive z directions. It rests on the xz plane.

We have used the concept of Display list in this class to draw the checkerboard. Other like giving the checkerboard lighting, material, ambient opengl function has been called.

4. DISPLAY - Though display is necessary for every application in gl programming, we had called it a separate module. Like all other gl programs, here we define to draw the objects on the screen.

Here we draws one frame, first the checkerboard and then the balls, from the current camera position.

5. USER INTERACTION - Without user interaction the program look dull, hence we have added user interaction to this program with special function (just named so).

4.5 KEY USES TO CONTROL

up Move camera up/zoom in

down Move camera down/zoom out

left Move camera left

right Move camera right

4.6 DIMENSIONAL VIEWING

Figure 4.6 3D Dimensional Viewing

4.7 LOW LEVEL DESIGN

Figure 4.7 Event Handler Map

4.1 FLOW DIAGRAM

Figure 4.8 Flow Diagram Of 3D Bouncing Ball

CHAPTER 5

IMPLEMENTATION

5.1 FUNCTIONS

The `glColor3f (float, float, float) :-` This function will set the current drawing color

`gluOrtho2D (GLdouble left, GLdouble right, GLdouble bottom, GLdouble top):-` which defines a two dimensional viewing rectangle in the plane $z=0$.

`glClear():-`Takes a single argument that is the bitwise OR of several values indicating which buffer is to be cleared.

`glClearColor ():-`Specifies the red, green, blue, and alpha values used by `glClear` to clear the color buffers.

`GLLoadIdentity():-`the current matrix with the identity matrix.

`glMatrixMode(mode):-`Sets the current matrix mode, mode can be `GL_MODELVIEW`, `GL_PROJECTION` or `GL_TEXTURE`.

`Void glutInit (int *argc, char**argv):-`Initializes GLUT, the arguments from main are passed in and can be used by the application.

`Void glutInitDisplayMode (unsigned int mode):-`Requests a display with the properties in mode. The value of mode is determined by the logical OR of options including the color model and buffering.

`Void glutInitWindowSize (int width, int height):-` Specifies the initial position of the topleft corner of the window in pixels

`Int glutCreateWindow (char *title):-`A window on the display. The string title can be used to label the window. The return value provides references to the window that can be used when there are multiple windows.

`Void glutMouseFunc(void *f(int button, int state, int x, int y):-`Register the mouse callback function f. The callback function returns the button, the state of button after the event and the position of the mouse relative to the top-left corner of the window.

`Void glutKeyboardFunc(void(*func) (void)):-`This function is called every time when you press enter key to resume the game or when you press 'b' or 'B' key to go back to the initial screen or when you press esc key to exit from the application.

`Void glutDisplayFunc (void (*func) (void)):-`Register the display function func that is executed when the window needs to be redrawn.

`Void glutSpecialFunc(void(*func)(void)):-`This function is called when you press the special keys in the keyboard like arrow keys, function keys etc. In our program.

5.2 FUNCTIONS USED TO SET THE VIEWING VOLUME

glOrtho

This function defines orthographic viewing volume with all parameters measured from the centre of projection. multiply the current matrix by a perspective matrix.

SYNTAX:

```
void glOrtho( GLdouble left, GLdouble right, GLdouble bottom, GLdouble top,  
GLdouble near, GLdouble far)
```

PARAMETERES:

- left, right - Specify the coordinates for the left and right vertical clipping planes.
- bottom, top - Specify the coordinates for the bottom and top horizontal clipping planes.
- nearVal, farVal - Specify the distances to the nearer and farther depth clipping planes. These values are negative if the plane is to be behind the viewer.

5.3 CALL BACK FUNCTIONS

glutDisplayFunc Function

glutDisplayFunc sets the display callback for the current window.

SYNTAX:

```
void glutDisplayFunc(void (*func)(void));
```

glutReshapeFunc Function

glutReshapeFunc sets the reshape callback for the current window.

SYNTAX:

```
void glutReshapeFunc(void (*func)(int width, int height));
```

5.4 MAIN FUNCTION

glutInit is used to initialize the GLUT library.

SYNTAX: glutInit(int *argc, char **argv);

PARAMETERS:

□ `argc` - A pointer to the program's unmodified `argc` variable from `main`. Upon return, the value pointed to by `argc` will be updated, because `glutInit` extracts any command line options intended for the GLUT library.

□ `argv` - The program's unmodified `argv` variable from `main`. Like `argc`, the data for `argv` will be updated because `glutInit` extracts any command line options understood by the GLUT library.

- `glutInit(&argc,argv);`

`glutInitDisplayMode` Function

`glutInitDisplayMode` sets the initial display mode.

SYNTAX:

```
void glutInitDisplayMode(unsigned int mode);
```

PARAMETERS:

□ `mode` - Display mode, normally the bitwise OR-ing of GLUT display mode bit masks. See values below:

`GLUT_RGB`: An alias for `GLUT_RGBA`.

`GLUT_DOUBLE`: Bit mask to select a double buffered window. This overrides

`GLUT_SINGLE`.

`GLUT_DEPTH`: Bit mask to select a window with a depth buffer.

`glutMainLoop` Function

`glutMainLoop` enters the GLUT event processing loop.

SYNTAX:

```
void glutMainLoop(void);
```

CHAPTER 6

SOURCE CODE

```
#include <iostream>

#ifdef __APPLE_CC__
#include <GLUT/glut.h>
#else
#include <GL/glut.h>
#endif

#include <cmath>

GLfloat WHITE[] = {1, 1, 1};
GLfloat RED[] = {1, 0, 0};
GLfloat GREEN[] = {0, 1, 0};
GLfloat MAGENTA[] = {1, 0, 1};

class Camera {
double theta;

double y;

double dTheta;

double dy;

public:
    Camera(): theta(0), y(3), dTheta(0.04), dy(0.2) {}

    double getX() {return 10 * cos(theta);}

    double getY() {return y;}

    double getZ() {return 10 * sin(theta);}

    void moveRight() {theta += dTheta;}

    void moveLeft() {theta -= dTheta;}

    void moveUp() {y += dy;}
}
```

```

void moveDown() {if (y > dy) y -= dy;}

};

class Ball {

double radius;

GLfloat* color;

double maximumHeight;

double x;

double y;

double z;

int direction;

public:

Ball(double r, GLfloat* c, double h, double x, double z):

    radius(r), color(c), maximumHeight(h), direction(-1),

    y(h), x(x), z(z) {

}

void update() {

y += direction * 0.05;

if (y > maximumHeight) {

y = maximumHeight; direction = -1;

} else if (y < radius) {

y = radius; direction = 1;

}

glPushMatrix();

glMaterialfv(GL_FRONT, GL_AMBIENT_AND_DIFFUSE, color);

glTranslated(x, y, z);

glutSolidSphere(radius, 30, 30);

glPopMatrix();

```

```

    }
};

class Checkerboard {

    int displayListId;

    int width;

    int depth;

public:

    Checkerboard(int width, int depth): width(width), depth(depth) {}

    double centerx() {return width / 2;}

    double centerz() {return depth / 2;}

    void create() {

        displayListId = glGenLists(1);

        glNewList(displayListId, GL_COMPILE);

        GLfloat lightPosition[] = {4, 3, 7, 1};

        glLightfv(GL_LIGHT0, GL_POSITION, lightPosition);

        glBegin(GL_QUADS);

        glNormal3d(0, 1, 0);

        for (int x = 0; x < width - 1; x++) {

            for (int z = 0; z < depth - 1; z++) {

                glMaterialfv(GL_FRONT, GL_AMBIENT_AND_DIFFUSE,

                    (x + z) % 2 == 0 ? RED : WHITE);

                glVertex3d(x, 0, z);

                glVertex3d(x+1, 0, z);

                glVertex3d(x+1, 0, z+1);

                glVertex3d(x, 0, z+1);

            }

        }

    }

    glEnd();
}

```

```

    glEndList();
}

void draw() {
    glCallList(displayListId);
}

};

Checkerboard checkerboard(8, 8);

Camera camera;

Ball balls[] = {
    Ball(1, GREEN, 7, 6, 1),
    Ball(1.5, MAGENTA, 6, 3, 4),
    Ball(0.4, WHITE, 5, 1, 7)
};

void init() {
    glEnable(GL_DEPTH_TEST);

    glLightfv(GL_LIGHT0, GL_DIFFUSE, WHITE);
    glLightfv(GL_LIGHT0, GL_SPECULAR, WHITE);
    glMaterialfv(GL_FRONT, GL_SPECULAR, WHITE);
    glMaterialf(GL_FRONT, GL_SHININESS, 30);

    glEnable(GL_LIGHTING);
    glEnable(GL_LIGHT0);

    checkerboard.create();
}

void display() {
    glClear(GL_COLOR_BUFFER_BIT | GL_DEPTH_BUFFER_BIT);

    glLoadIdentity();

```

```

gluLookAt(camera.getX(), camera.getY(), camera.getZ(),
          checkerboard.centerx(), 0.0, checkerboard.centerz(),
          0.0, 1.0, 0.0);

checkerboard.draw();

for (int i = 0; i < sizeof balls / sizeof(Ball); i++) {
    balls[i].update();
}

glFlush();

glutSwapBuffers();
}

void reshape(GLint w, GLint h) {
    glViewport(0, 0, w, h);

    glMatrixMode(GL_PROJECTION);

    glLoadIdentity();

    gluPerspective(40.0, GLfloat(w) / GLfloat(h), 1.0, 150.0);

    glMatrixMode(GL_MODELVIEW);
}

void timer(int v) {
    glutPostRedisplay();

    glutTimerFunc(1000/60, timer, v);
}

void special(int key, int, int) {
    switch (key) {
        case GLUT_KEY_LEFT: camera.moveLeft(); break;
        case GLUT_KEY_RIGHT: camera.moveRight(); break;
        case GLUT_KEY_UP: camera.moveUp(); break;
    }
}

```

```
    case GLUT_KEY_DOWN: camera.moveDown(); break;
}

glutPostRedisplay();
}

int main(int argc, char** argv) {
    glutInit(&argc, argv);
    glutInitDisplayMode(GLUT_DOUBLE | GLUT_RGB | GLUT_DEPTH);
    glutInitWindowPosition(80, 80);
    glutInitWindowSize(800, 600);
    glutCreateWindow("3D Bouncing Balls");
    glutDisplayFunc(display);
    glutReshapeFunc(reshape);
    glutSpecialFunc(special);
    glutTimerFunc(100, timer, 0);
    init();
    glutMainLoop();
}
```


Figure 7.1
Rotating
View of 3D
Bouncing
Ball

Figure 7.2 Side View of 3D Bouncing Ball

Figure 7.3 Zooming In 3D Bouncing Ball

Figure 7.4 Zooming Out 3D Bouncing Ball

Figure 7.5 Stopping The Balls on Air

Figure 7.6 Viewing Shining Surface in 3D Bouncing Ball

CHAPTER 8

CONCLUSION

In this 3D Bouncing Ball OpenGL Programming, a timer is also there which requests to draw the next frame. Also the size of the ball and colors are hard-coded which can be change with global array. Similarly size and color of checkerboard is hard-code which also can be changed via program. We have used navigation key for user interaction. GL Programming is programming with use of opengl graphics library. OpenGL API contains several functions, which helps rendering 2D/3D image as graphics on computer. It is designed to streamline the process of rendering the different objects on computer screen. One of the best part that OpenGL has over DirectX is that, OpenGL is hardware/OS independent. First the floor is drawn which is a checkerboard, most likely similar to our opengl chess board program. we are created an application which shows the balls bouncing on a Chess Board.

REFERENCE AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Acharya, Kamal, Attendance Management System Project (April 28, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4810251> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4810251>
2. Acharya, Kamal, Online Food Order System (May 2, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814732> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814732>
3. Acharya, Kamal, University management system project. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814103> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814103>
4. Acharya, Kamal, Online banking management system. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4813597> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4813597>
5. Acharya, Kamal, Online Job Portal Management System (May 5, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4817534> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4817534>
6. Acharya, Kamal, Employee leave management system. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819626> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819626>
7. Acharya, Kamal, Online electricity billing project report. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819630> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819630>
8. Acharya, Kamal, POLICY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831694> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831694>
9. Acharya, Kamal, Online job placement system project report. (January 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831638> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831638>
10. Acharya, Kamal, Software testing for project report. (May 16, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831028> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831028>
11. Acharya, Kamal, ONLINE CRIME REPORTING SYSTEM PROJECT. (August 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831015> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831015>
12. Acharya, Kamal, Burger ordering system project report. (October 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4832704> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4832704>
13. Acharya, Kamal, Teachers Record Management System Project Report (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4833821> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4833821>
14. Acharya, Kamal, Dairy Management System Project Report (December 20, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835231> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835231>
15. Acharya, Kamal, Electrical Shop Management System Project (December 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835238> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835238>
16. Acharya, Kamal, Online book store management system project report. (February 10, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835277> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835277>
17. Acharya, Kamal, Paint shop management system project report. (January 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835441> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835441>
18. Acharya, Kamal, Supermarket billing system project report. (August 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835474> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835474>
19. Acharya, Kamal, Online taxi booking system project report. (March 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837729> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837729>
20. Acharya, Kamal, Online car servicing system project report. (March 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837832> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837832>
21. Acharya, Kamal, School management system project report. (July 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837837> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837837>

22. Acharya, Kamal, Furniture Showroom Management System Project Report (March 21, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839422> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839422>
23. Acharya, Kamal, Online Vehicle Rental System Project Report (March 21, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839429> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839429>
24. Acharya, Kamal, Fruit Shop Management System Project Report (August 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841048> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841048>
25. Acharya, Kamal, Hall Booking Management System Project Report (December 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841055> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841055>
26. Acharya, Kamal, Laundry Management System Project Report (October 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841059> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841059>
27. Acharya, Kamal, A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT (September 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841209> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841209>
28. Acharya, Kamal, A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT (May 25, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841210> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841210>
29. Acharya, Kamal, ONLINE DATING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842066> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842066>
30. Acharya, Kamal, ONLINE RESUME BUILDER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842071> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842071>
31. Acharya, Kamal, TOLL TEX MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT (August 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842082> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842082>
32. Acharya, Kamal, Chat Application Through Client Server Management System Project Report (June 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842761> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842761>
33. Acharya, Kamal, Web Chatting Application Management System Project Report (April 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842771> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842771>
34. Acharya, Kamal, Automobile management system project report (May 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846917> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846917>
35. Acharya, Kamal, College bus management system project report (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846920> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846920>
36. Acharya, Kamal, Courier management system project report (May 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846922> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846922>
37. Acharya, Kamal, Event management system project report (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846927> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846927>
38. Acharya, Kamal, Library management system project report II (May 25, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4848857> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4848857>
39. Kamal Acharya. Teacher record management system project report. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.46787329/v1>
40. Kamal Acharya. POST OFFICE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.44494375/v1>
41. Kamal Acharya. Fruit shop management system project report. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.42227675/v1>
42. Kamal Acharya. Dairy management system project report. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261513.39402347/v1>
43. Kamal Acharya. DATA COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER NETWORK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.37480177/v1>
44. Kamal Acharya. School management system project report. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.34023165/v1>
45. Kamal Acharya. A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.30191075/v1>

46. Kamal Acharya. A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT. Authorea. August 01, 2024
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254872.26972790/v1>
47. Kamal Acharya. Web chatting application project report management system. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.18588592/v1>
48. Kamal Acharya. RETAIL STORE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.14590154/v1>
49. Kamal Acharya. SUPERMARKET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.19145062/v1>
50. Kamal Acharya. SOCIAL MEDIA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.11210579/v1>
51. Kamal Acharya. Online music portal management system project report. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252488.89734698/v1>
52. Kamal Acharya. COLLEGE BUS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245277.70798942/v1>
53. Kamal Acharya. AUTOMOBILE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245276.67982593/v1>
54. Kamal Acharya. Ludo management system project report. Authorea. July 31, 2024
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243999.98091616/v1>
55. Kamal Acharya. Literature online quiz system project report. Authorea. July 31, 2024
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243825.53562953/v1>
56. Kamal Acharya. Avoid waste management system project. Authorea. July 29, 2024
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228528.85022205/v1>
57. Kamal Acharya. CHAT APPLICATION THROUGH CLIENT SERVER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT. Authorea. July 29, 2024.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228527.74316529/v1>
58. Kamal Acharya. Parking allotment system project report. Authorea. July 29, 2024.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172227078.89966943/v1>
59. Kamal Acharya. HEALTH INSURANCE CLAIM MANAGEMENT SYSTEM. Authorea. July 26, 2024.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172202020.06707762/v1>
60. Kamal Acharya. ONLINE TRAIN BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 22, 2024.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172167914.45160406/v1>
61. Kamal Acharya. COVID MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 16, 2024.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172116616.60220024/v1>
62. Kamal Acharya. COVID MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 16, 2024.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172116616.60220024/v1>